

GENETIC DIVERGENCE IN COLOCASIA(*Colocasiaesculenta* var. *antiquorum*) GERMPLASMS UNDER EASTERN UTTAR PRADESH REGIONManvendra Singh^{1#}, G.C. Yadav^{2*} and Vimlesh Kumar³^{1,2}Department of Vegetable Science, COH&F, ANDUAT, Kumarganj Ayodhya³Assistant Professor (Hort.), College of Agriculture, Azamgarh, ANDUAT, Kumarganj Ayodhya

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Abstract

The present investigation was conducted with aim to know the genetic diversity among the genotypes of *Colocasia/taro(arvi)* collected from the different locations. The trial was conducted at two different locations viz., main Experimental Station of Department of Vegetable Science, ANDUAT, Kumarganj Ayodhya and village Belakhra farmer's field Ayodhya during March to August, 2015 and 2016. The investigation conducted with forty taro genotypes including two check varieties to assess the extent of genetic diversity by D^2 analysis. The trials were conducted in Randomized Block Design replicated thrice. Observations were recorded on sixteen quantitative characters which included leaf, petiole, corm, cormel and corm characters. The analysis was conducted for D^2 analysis which concluded that the characters like as leaf area, corm weight per plant, cormel weight per plant and yield per plant contributed the maximum towards diversity. The forty genotypes were grouped into six clusters where eight genotypes grouped in cluster I and III while, cluster II, IV, V and VI had three, two, five and four genotypes, respectively. The intra cluster distance was more in cluster VI and the inter cluster distance was maximum between cluster II and cluster VI. Therefore, crosses between members of clusters separated by high inter-cluster distances are likely to produce desirable segregates.

Keywords: Genetic divergence, taro/arvi, cluster mean, cluster distance, grouping

Introduction

Colocasia (Colocasiaesculenta var. *antiquorum*) also known as 'Taro' is one of the oldest known tuber crop and has been grown for more than 10,000 years ago in Tropical Asia (Lebot, 2009). It is a tropical tuber crop belongs to the monocotyledonous own family Araceae of the order Arales whose participants are called aroids (Henry, 2001). Family Araceae includes about 100 genera and 1500 widely distributed species. It has been probably originated as of the wet tropical place flanked by India and Indonesia (Matthews, 2004) and has been cultivated within the South Pacific for hundreds of years (FAO, 1992). In Asia, average yields reach 12.6 t ha⁻¹ (FAOSTAT, 2019). Tuber crops are classified through their hardness to varying environmental conditions which are in advance global significance among bigger demand to increase diversity to maintain crop production. Further being a wealthy supply of vitamins, carbohydrates, minerals, proteins and dietary fibre (Bradburry and Holloway, 1998), colocasia too possesses therapeutic values in opposition to tuberculosis, fungal infection and ulcers (Singh *et al.*, 2012). It is mainly cultivated in Eastern and Southern States. Faizabad, Varanasi, Sitapur, Sultanpur, and some parts of Jhansi, Deoria etc. are the leading districts with regard to Arvi production particularly in Eastern districts of Uttar Pradesh.

The corms and cormels are mostly used as vegetables or as subsidiary food after roasting, baking or boiling. Young leaves and petioles are widely consumed as vegetable. The corms and cormels are rich in starch which contains 17-25 per cent amylase. Its flour is considered good baby food because its starch is easily digestible. It helps in constipation problems and supplements iron (Onwueme, 1999). The nutritive value of colocasia per 100g of corms and cormels contains moisture 73.1g, carbohydrate 21.1g, protein 3.1g, fat 0.1g, β -carotene 24 μ g, thiamine 0.09mg, riboflavin 0.03mg, calcium 40mg, and iron 1.7mg which can be used as supplements of these nutrients. The genotypic similarity and repetition of genotypes with the name of different accession and differentiation among them can be made easy by genetic divergence study which gives guide lines in accessing the of diverse genotypes and further creation of variability / F_1 . Mahalanobis D^2 analysis helps in the assessment of genetic diversity among the genotypes and contribution of each character to total diversity.

Material and Method

The experimental material were comprised of forty genotype collected from All India Co-ordinate Research project on Tuber Crops. The experiments were carried out at two location i.e. ANDUAT Kumarganj, Ayodhya, UP and Farmer's field Belakhra, Ayodhya, UP for two consecutive seasons of year 2015 and 2016 in the randomized block design with three replications. Cormels of each genotype was planted in the month of March at inter and intra row spacing of 60 cm having plot size of: 2.40m x 1.80 m. The standard packages of practices were followed to raise the crops. Morphological observation were recorded on five randomly selected plants from each plot and replication for days to sprouting, length of leaf (cm), width of leaf (cm), girth of plant (cm), petiole length (cm), sheath length (cm), height of plant (cm), length of cormels (cm), girth of cormels (cm), number of cormels /plant, weight cormels /plant (g), length of corm (cm), girth of corms (cm), weight of corms /plant (g), dry matter (%), yield / plant (g). Genetic divergence analysis was performed as per Mahalanobis (1936) D^2 statistics and clustering of genotypes was done by using Tochers method (Rao, 1952).

Result and Discussion

In pooled analysis of present investigation, the forty genotypes of taro were grouped into seven distinct non-overlapping clusters (Table-1). This indicated the presence of considerable diversity in the genotypes. The major cluster in the above mentioned genetic divergence analysis contained frequently the genotypes of heterogeneous origin. Although, the genotypes of same origin or geographic region were also found to be grouped together in the same cluster. The instances of grouping of genotypes of different origin or geographic region in same cluster were frequently observed. This suggested that there is no parallelism between genetic and geographic diversity. Cluster IV had highest number of genotypes (8) followed by cluster II and V (7), cluster VI (6), cluster II (5), cluster VII (4) and cluster I recorded only (3) genotypes which indicates that these genotypes have their own identity and there no similarity with other genotypes.

The estimates of intra and inter-cluster distances represented by D^2 values are given in table no. 2. Perusal of table number 2 indicated that the maximum inter-cluster distance was observed between clusters I and IV (248.36). This, suggested that members of these two clusters are genetically very diverse to each other. The minimum inter-cluster value was recorded in case of cluster VI and cluster VI (78.26). The

higher inter-cluster distance indicated greater genetic divergence between the genotypes of those clusters while, lower inter-cluster values between the clusters suggested that the genotypes of the clusters were not much genetically diverse from each other. Similar finding were also recorded by Devi *et al.* (2013) and Bhadauria *et al.* (2013).

The clusters means for sixteen characters in taro (pooled) had given in table -3. The highest cluster mean for days to sprouting was found in case of cluster VI (17.01) followed by cluster VII (16.30) and lowest cluster mean for this trait in cluster III (13.70). The highest cluster mean for length of leaf (cm) was found in case of cluster IV (49.28) followed by cluster VII (48.30). The lowest cluster mean for length of leaf (cm) was recorded cluster I (30.37). The highest cluster mean for width of leaf (cm) was found in case of cluster IV (40.72) followed by cluster VI (39.94). The lowest cluster mean for width of leaf (cm) cluster I was recorded (24.89). The highest cluster mean for girth of plant (cm) was found in case of cluster VI (18.13), followed by cluster II (18.00). cluster V (17.02). The lowest clusters mean for girth of plant (cm) was recorded in case of cluster III (16.78). The highest cluster mean for petiole length (cm) was found in case of cluster I (25.52) followed by cluster IV (24.38). The lowest clusters mean for petiole length (cm) was found in case of cluster I (16.75). The highest cluster mean for sheath length (cm) was found in case of cluster II (24.33) followed by cluster VII (21.61). The lowest clusters mean for sheath length (cm) was found in case cluster I (15.25). The highest cluster mean for height of Plant (cm) was found in case of cluster VII (87.74) followed by cluster VI (87.52). cluster II (67.53). The lowest cluster mean for height of Plant (cm) was recorded in case of cluster I (59.92). The highest cluster mean for length of cormel (cm) was found in case of cluster VIII (6.79) followed by cluster VI (6.61). The lowest cluster mean length of cormel (cm) was recorded in case of cluster II (5.82). The highest cluster mean for girth of cormels (cm) was found in case of cluster VII (7.94) followed by cluster IV (7.89). The lowest cluster mean for girth of cormels was recorded in case of cluster II (6.89). The highest cluster mean for number of cormels per plant was found in case of cluster IV (22.89) followed by cluster III (16.12). The lowest cluster mean was recorded in case of cluster I (12.25). The highest cluster mean for weight of cormels per plant (g) was found in case of cluster III (468.48) followed by cluster IV (418.27). The lowest cluster mean for weight of cormels per plant (g) was recorded in case of cluster VI (260.78). The highest cluster mean length of corm (cm) was found in case of cluster I (9.83) followed by cluster IV (9.63), cluster III (9.46), cluster VII (9.42), cluster VI (9.37) and cluster V (9.26). The lowest clusters mean for length of corm (cm) was recorded in case of cluster II (8.99). The highest cluster mean girth of corms (cm) was found in case of cluster IV (24.99) followed by cluster VII (20.44), cluster I (20.41), cluster III (19.71), cluster V (18.96) and cluster II (18.45). The lowest clusters mean for girth of corms (cm) was recorded in case of cluster IV (15.27). The highest cluster mean weight of corms per plant (g) was found in case of cluster VI (168.82) followed by cluster I (111.02), cluster V (109.80), cluster VII (99.36), cluster II (95.80) and cluster IV (95.65). The lowest clusters mean for weight of corms per plant (g) was recorded in case of cluster III (93.36). The highest cluster mean for dry matter content was found in case of cluster VI (21.45) followed by cluster IV (20.84), cluster III (20.68), cluster V (20.64), cluster I (20.57) and cluster II (20.50). The lowest clusters mean for dry matter content was recorded in case of cluster VII (20.42). The highest cluster mean yield per plant was found in case of cluster III (561.84) followed by cluster IV (513.92), cluster VI (504.43), cluster V

(479.00), cluster I (440.61) and cluster II (427.37). The lowest clusters mean for yield per plant was recorded in case of cluster VII (360.17).

Highest percent contribution of characters towards total genetic divergence between forty genotypes of taro had been given table -4. The maximum contribution in manifestation of total genetic divergence was made by weight of cormels per plant (30.64%) followed by length of leaf (25.51%), weight of corms per plant (12.05%), height of plant (11.41%), number of cormels per plant (6.41%), petiole length (5.26%), sheath length (3.46%), dry matter content (1.92%), days to sprouting (1.67%), girth of corms (1.03%), length of corm (0.51%), and width of leaf (0.13%) were very low in manifestation of total genetic divergence in the available germplasm.

Conclusion

It might be very conveniently concluded that there is a great possibility for improvement in the desired attributes to this seemingly high valuable vegetable crop.

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Table 1: Clustering pattern of 40 genotypes of colocasia on the basis of Mahalanobis D² statistics (Pooled).

Cluster number	No. of genotypes	Genotypes
I.	3	NDC-6, NDC-7 NDC-36
II.	5	NDC-10, NDC-12 , NDC-21, NDC-24, NDC-29
III.	7	NDC-8, NDC-17, NDC-19, NDC-20, NDC-22,NDC-26, NDC-31
IV.	8	NDC-9, NDC-11, NDC-15, NDC-18, NDC-25, NDC-33. NDC-1 (C), NDC-2(C)
V.	7	NDC-13,NDC-14,NDC-23,NDC-27,NDC-28,NDC-30,NDC-35
VI.	6	NDC-16,NDC-32,NDC-34,NDC-38,NDC-39,NDC-40
VII.	4	NDC-3,NDC-4,NDC-5,NDC-37

Table 2: Average of intra- and inter-clusters D² values for seven clusters in colocasia(Pooled).

Cluster number	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII
I	56.57	97.50	152.35	248.36	161.54	133.29	214.45
II		53.15	146.32	184.01	109.88	113.93	141.67
III			71.51	121.21	112.87	170.64	233.54
IV				48.16	74.48	177.45	154.01
VI					43.45	89.66	78.26
VI						61.77	112.44
VII							35.91

Table No.3: Intra- cluster group means for sixteen characters incolocasia (Pooled).

Character Cluster No.	Days to sprouting	Length of leaf (cm)	Width of leaf (cm)	Girth of plant (cm)	Petiole length (cm)	Sheath length (cm)	Height of Plant (cm)	Length of cormel (cm)	Girth of cormels (cm)	Number of cormels per Plant	Weight of cormels per plant(g)	Length of corm (cm)	Girth of corms (cm)	Weight of corms per plant (g)	Dry matter (%)	Yield per Plant(g)
I	15.05	30.37	24.89	17.10	16.75	15.25	59.92	6.56	7.57	12.25	329.59	9.83	20.41	111.02	20.57	440.61
II	15.63	33.53	26.60	18.00	25.52	24.33	67.53	5.82	6.89	14.93	331.57	8.99	18.45	95.80	20.50	427.37
III	13.70	36.63	29.54	16.78	17.65	19.25	82.85	6.20	7.21	16.12	468.48	9.46	19.71	93.36	20.68	561.84
IV	14.90	49.28	40.72	18.09	24.38	19.81	85.56	6.58	7.89	22.89	418.27	9.63	17.88	95.65	20.84	513.92
V	15.63	44.92	37.26	17.02	24.10	20.06	85.84	6.47	7.66	16.03	369.82	9.26	18.96	109.80	20.64	479.00
VI	17.01	37.56	30.55	18.13	23.24	20.32	87.52	6.61	7.59	15.38	335.62	9.37	24.99	168.82	21.45	504.43
VII	16.30	48.43	39.94	17.39	23.44	21.61	87.74	6.79	7.94	12.96	260.78	9.42	20.44	99.39	20.42	360.17

Table 4: Percent contribution of sixteen characters towards total genetic divergence in colocasia(Pooled).

S.No.	Source	Times Ranked I St	Percent Contribution
1	Days to sprouting	13	1.67
2	Length of leaf (cm)	199	25.51
3	Width of leaf (cm)	1	0.13
4	Girth of plant (cm)	0	0.01
5	Petiole length (cm)	41	5.26
6	Sheath length (cm)	27	3.46
7	Height of Plant (cm)	89	11.41
8	Length of cormel(cm)	0	0.01
9	Girth of cormels (cm)	0	0.01
10	Number ofcormelsperPlant	50	6.41
11	Weigh ofcormelsperplant(g)	239	30.64
12	Length of corm (cm)	4	0.51
13	Girth of corms (cm)	8	1.03
14	Weight of corms per plant (g)	94	12.05
15	Dry Matter %	15	1.92
16	Yield per Plant (g)	0	0.01